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Awareness Level of Social Work Students of the Phenomenon of Violence Based on Gender

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at investigating the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of violence based on gender and their attitudes towards it. The study sample consisted of (476) male and female students. The study followed a research methodology relying on the descriptive analytical approach and adopted the questionnaire as a research tool. The study results revealed a high awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of violence based on gender, with an arithmetic mean of (3.91) and a standard deviation of (0.77) on all the dimensions of the measure. In addition, the results of statistical analysis showed that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the students' awareness level of the phenomenon of violence based on gender which can be attributed to the study variables. According to the study results, some appropriate recommendations are presented.

Keywords: Students' awareness level, Social work students, Violence in the familial environment, Phenomenon of violence based on gender, Husband assault.

INTRODUCTION

Human societies face an increase in needs and social problems, which requires dealing with these needs and problems in a scientific and planned manner. Social work is one of the human professions assuming a big role in facing those needs and social problems, where the philosophy of the profession is based on supporting the weak and less lucky societal categories, aiming at helping them overcome their problems and face the challenges that they encounter; consequently, empowering them and reinforcing their abilities. The phenomenon of violence based on gender is considered one of the social problems with which the profession of social work is concerned with the aim of treating this problem in a scientific manner.

The phenomenon of violence based on gender has recently increased and widely spread as a result of the nature of the contemporary life and its accompanying transitions and changes that caused the appearance of some social and familial problems which were not present before in many traditional societies. The phenomenon of violence based on gender can be described as a negative social phenomenon that changed the society from a conventional pattern into another civilized, developed pattern (Al-Ayesh, 2016).

In light of that change, families also were subject to some changes that caused large effects; socially, culturally and economically, so that families lost some of their functions and experienced a disorder which disturbed the value of cooperation and solidarity at the level of the whole familial pattern.

Many studies indicated that the phenomenon of violence based on gender is a global phenomenon which takes different forms according to the progress level of nations, where it is more widely spread among families in developing countries' societies compared to those in the societies of developed countries (Oyediran, 2005). Also, it was observed that the rates of violence based on gender increase in war times and when there are armed conflicts, particularly rates of rape (ICRW, 2009). In the Jordanian society, statistics showed that the phenomenon of violence against wives has recently remarkably increased, where the number of physical violence cases announced against women during the third quarter of 2020 amounted to (4678) cases, noting that this increase was the result of different reasons among which is the comprehensive ban imposed by the government of Jordan because of Covid-19 pandemic (Family Protection Administration, 2020). The problem of violence based on gender is a social problem that increases as a result of acceleration of material and technological changes that are not coped with by the social changes at the level of the society's values, habits and traditions (Hinkle, 1994).

In the Jordanian society, even after the increase in the woman's economic participation rate amounting to (15%) according to the General Statistics Department for the year 2018 and the improvement in her status at different levels, the working woman still suffers from social problems resulting from the duality of her roles as a

house manager, a mother and a wife on the one hand and her role as a working woman who works outside the house for long hours on the other hand, which contributed to an increase in the rates of violence directed against her as a result of this contradiction. According to many specialists, the woman witnesses nowadays a crisis in her marital life because of her work outside the house (Al-Hassan, 2008).

Based on the discussion above, the current study deals with an important social category in the society; namely, the university youth specialized in social work and sheds light on the role of social work profession in mitigating the phenomenon of violence based on gender. This is achieved through monitoring the position of university youth and investigating their awareness level of the role of social work in reducing this phenomenon, noting that social work has not at all been far from this societal category in all conditions and ages. Social work has entered the field of women's care and protection from violence, where the social specialist became a member of the work team at the family protection institutions. Therefore, the opinions and attitudes of social work students who will become social specialists in the future about social work care of women who are victims of violence affect their professional preparation as well as the ways of dealing with this category of women subjected to violence.

Problem of Study

Being concerned with women subjected to violence is an issue that has attracted the attention of scientists in different psychological, social and medical disciplines, noting that this societal category deserves a lot of care and support because of being subject to continuous assaults and violations. Many international studies showed that violence based on gender has its cultural roots in masculine societies which differ according to educational level, familial economic status and the level of commitment to religious beliefs (UNICEF, 2000). In spite of enhanced statistics indicating a progress in the status of the woman in the Jordanian society at the levels of education, economic and political participation, there are other figures that indicate an increase in the number of women who are subjected to numerous types of violence based on gender according to cases and issues registered by the Family Protection Administration.

Considering the problem of gender-based violence, we find that social work profession plays an important role in facing the problem of familial violence and has

also a vital role in the field of taking care of women who have been subjected to one or another type of violence. Social work profession assumes a big responsibility through its numerous institutions and well-trained social specialists. In addition, departments of social work at Jordanian universities are preparing social work students, both theoretically and practically, in order to help them acquire knowledge, skills and experiences necessary to practice the profession in general or in one of its domains. So, the researcher recognized the necessity of investigating the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of violence based on gender, being a major domain of Jordanian social work.

Study Importance

The importance of this study lies in the following points:

1. This study is intended to provide theoretical literature and previous studies on the study's topic (Awareness Level of Social Work Students of the Phenomenon of Violence Based on Gender), thereby paving the way for researchers and those interested in this field to conduct more studies connected to women who are victims of violence.
2. The continuous increase in the numbers of women subjected to one or more forms of violence can't be ignored and deserves studying, follow-up and concern in order to provide this societal category with care and support. In the Jordanian society, according to the information of Family Protection Administration, the number of women who were subjected to violence in 2020 amounted to (4678), which points to the importance of studying this topic.
3. The Jordanian environment is in need of this type of study, emanating from the importance of the study sample (social work students), as well as the importance of detecting the characteristics and non-knowledge capacities of this sample, which adds to the credit of scientific information on it.
4. It is attempted to monitor differences in some main variables adopted in the study in forming the position of the study sample towards the phenomenon of gender-based violence and the role of social work in mitigating this phenomenon.
5. The study can be considered an attempt to construct a database that forms the fundament in forming the knowledge base which should contribute to planning of

awareness programs aiming at raising the familial awareness associated with gender-based violence issues, as well as activating the protective aspect and consequently benefiting from the collected data in theoretical and practical research pertinent to the subject of gender-based violence.

Study Objectives

The main objective of this study is to investigate the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence and their attitudes towards it. This field is one of the main fields of social work.

This main objective can be segmented into the following sub-objectives:

- 1- Investigating social work students' awareness of the causes of gender-based violence.
- 2- Investigating social work students' awareness of the forms of gender-based violence.
- 3- Investigating the view of social work students towards the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women subjected to violence.
- 4- Revealing the existence of statistically significant differences -if any- at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the awareness level of social work students of the gender-based violence phenomenon which can be attributed to the variables of gender (male, female), academic level (year 1,2,3) and family educational level (high, low).

Research Questions

- 1- What is the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence and their attitudes towards it?
- 2- What is the awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence?
- 3- What is the awareness level of social work students of the forms of gender-based violence?
- 4- How do social work students view the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women subjected to violence?

- 5- Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the awareness level of social work students of the gender-based violence phenomenon which can be attributed to the variables of gender (male, female), academic level (year 1,2,3) and family educational level (high, low).

Study Concepts

- 1- Violence: “a state that reflects the society’s health and security and results from the ignorance of the human’s economic, social, political and institutional needs; including material and immaterial harm that causes destruction, pain, injury and fear (Redcross, 2002:1).
- 2- Gender-based Violence: In spite of the non-existence of a unified definition of gender-based violence as a result of multiplicity of human cultures and diversity of this type of violence, some specialists defined gender-based violence as “any action or threat that results in a harm or a physical, sexual or psychological suffering; or results in denial or obligation in terms of freedom, either being in general or private life. Gender-based violence includes sexual and home violence, as well as sex trade, harmful practices like circumcision and early marriage, prostitution, solicitation and all forms of sexual abuse” (Duvvury and Galway, 2009).
- 3- A Woman Subjected to Violence: “a woman who is subjected to a verbal, symbolic or physical behavior or act of aggression by her husband or partner with the aim of subjugating her or abusing her in the frame of a non-equivalent relationship” (Awwad, 2012).
- 4- Awareness Level of Social Work Students: it is the degree determined by social work students at Jordanian universities of their agreement with the expressions (items’ content) representing the gender-based violence phenomenon.
- 5- Social Work Students: students who passed successfully the general secondary exam and are sitting on study seats in the departments of social work at the Jordanian universities in the discipline of social work.

Theoretical Framework and Reference Studies

The appearance of violence in societies reflects their cultures, behavior patterns, beliefs and attitudes of dealing with their individuals as well as the ways used by societies to resolve conflicts that arise inside them. There are several forms and types of

gender-based violence (Richardson et al., 2002), but the most obvious form of violence to the public is the physical violence that refers to using physical force intentionally against the woman to harm her and cause her big damage; like using hands, legs or any tool which leaves clear effects on the body of the assaulted woman (Peedicayil et al., 2004).

Thomas Hobbes is considered among the first thinkers who emphasized that the origin of the human's normal state is the evil and that aggression and violence represent an essential tendency in individuals.

Emil Durkheim indicated that societies witness a transition from simple societies to complex ones as a result of moral density. Throughout the stages of this transition, the society is subjected to social and economic changes that affect its fundamental structures, leaving deep impacts on social systems and phenomena. As a result, the system of values and standards is affected and the social environment becomes suitable to an increase of the violence phenomenon at several levels starting from the family, as it is considered the first social system affected by value and standard changes in the society (Jamil, 2007).

The gender-based violence phenomenon represents a particularly complicated problem which is associated with many factors and variables each of which contributes to its occurrence, such as economic, cultural, social and political factors, among others, which pushed modern societies, international organizations, governmental institutions and civil society entities to be concerned with this phenomenon, where such concern represents a criterion that measures the civilization of peoples and societies. In addition, the phenomenon of gender-based violence has become an issue of human rights and democracy. As other societies, the Jordanian society suffers from negative social phenomena that affect its social structure and the nature of social relations among individuals. Familial violence is a negative social phenomenon which has increased and widely spread recently as a result of the nature of contemporary life and its accompanying transitions and changes that led to the appearance of some social and familial problems that have not been existent in traditional societies (Al-Ayesh, 2016).

It is worth mentioning that weakness of internal means of social control, represented in conscience and sentiment saturated with values, habits and traditions of

the society, leads to the society's loss of its power in deterring deviating behavior that harms others, such as violence against women (Bruckner, 2006).

Most of the studies conducted in many Arab countries on the familial violence phenomenon indicate that violence against the wife is the most famous and widely spread type of familial violence in our societies and that the wife is the first victim of familial violence. Attention to studying violence against the wife has increased since the 1970s, noting that the problem of violence against the wife was not sufficiently known and there were no women's protection programs or protection houses to shelter assaulted women and their children. Also, there were no counseling or treatment programs before that time (New Man, 1993). This concern came as a response of the woman's liberation movements that extended all over the world. The UN has endorsed the resolution no. (18) of the year (1991) which stated the necessity of preventing violence against women, in addition to announcing the 25th of November an annual international day of fighting violence against the woman.

As a result of expansion of gender-based violence in both developed and developing societies, the attention of researchers and specialists in the field of social and familial sciences regarding studying the phenomenon of familial violence and its reflections on the society has increased, through following up its causes and factors leading to it, as well as suggesting appropriate solutions to it. This is because violence against the wife leaves negative effects on the wife's psychological and physical health and consequently affects the psychological health of the whole family (Hassan, 2001).

In light of the increasing civilization rates, cities tend to more expansion and the internal means of social control go back to the benefit of external means of social control represented in laws, security instruments and courts which assume the tasks of preventing and punishing deviating behaviours such as violence (Al-Hassan and Al-Ahmad, 2009).

Social work profession is a human profession that plays a big role in facing social challenges that encounter societies, where the philosophy of social service profession relies on supporting weak and marginalized categories and less lucky people and aims at helping the individual overcome his/her problems and face challenges that he/she encounters, in addition to meeting his/her needs and desires, which leads to empower the individual and reinforce his/her capabilities. Consequently, social work profession

focuses on encountering the familial problems that face husband and wife through positive professional intervention and helping them overcome marital conflicts and face life challenges. Social work profession relies on a scientific base of knowledge, human sciences and practicing experiences in order to create positive social change through working in the familial field. Social work in the familial field is practiced by academically qualified, sufficiently trained social specialists who are committed to the profession's values. It depends on knowledge, skills and ethics, where social work in the familial environment evaluates familial problems and diagnoses them upon their occurrence, especially in their initial stages. It also investigates the size of problems and the level of psychological health of the family members, in addition to studying strengths and weaknesses in the family's structure, especially between husband and wife; thereby aiming at enhancing the quality of marital life and achieving marital consistency, as well as protecting the family from problems facing it as a result of different life conditions and consequently protecting the familial pattern against decomposition and maintaining the family's continuity and cohesion.

Abeer Yousef (2020) conducted a study aiming at investigating the problems of the woman subjected to violence and the role of common practice in social service in reducing them. The study concluded that the husband's poverty is a main cause of practicing violence on the wife, in addition to the existence of important roles in the work of the social specialist that help in reducing the familial violence phenomenon.

Hawasa Jamal (2019) conducted a study entitled: "The Role of Social Service in Reducing Familial Problems: Familial Violence As a Model". The study confirmed the importance of the applied dimension and the professional practice in reducing familial violence in the Algerian society.

Al-Awawdeh (2018) studied the attitudes of social socialists towards the cases of gender-based violence and found that the skill and knowledge level of social specialists is still lower than required in the field of familial violence.

Al-Mufti and Al-Arabeed (2018) conducted a study entitled: "Professional View of General Practice in Social Service to Deal with Women Who Are Victims of Violence". They revealed the necessity of the acquisition of women who are subject to violence of the necessary skills and strategies in confronting violence imposed on them.

Yousef Awwad (2012) investigated the factors associated with the woman which cause her to be subject to violence by her husband from the perspective of psychological, social and law specialists working with women subject to violence. The study revealed no statistically significant differences between the means of the sample members' responses attributed to the study variables. Further, social factors occupied the first rank in practicing violence against women.

Leung (2011) studied the gender sensitivity in social specialists dealing with familial violence cases in Hong Kong and found that familial violence treatment requires mediation and compromise as a result of the occurrence of a disturbance in the relationship of forces between man and woman.

Qassim (2009) conducted a study entitled: "Towards a Suggested Program to Develop Social Specialists' Skills in Working with Familial Violence Cases". He found that social specialists possess a group of professional skills that qualify them to work with familial violence victims.

In the Jordanian society, some studies indicated the presence of a proportional relationship between the rate of family size and the level of violence in the family, where (49.5%) of the Jordanian families in which familial violence occurs consist of (5-9) members, while families with (1-4) members exhibit a violence percentage of (30.6%). Moreover, those studies indicated the existence of an inverse relationship between the educational level of familial violence issues' parties and the occurrence of familial violence, where statistics indicated that in 2011, the percentage of familial violence committers with low educational level amounted to (62.2%) (Al-Hunaiti et al., 2012).

The current study is distinguished from previous studies in that it is concerned with the phenomenon of gender-based violence from the viewpoint of social work students to investigate their beliefs on this subject. Regarding the relation of the subject with social work, it is worth mentioning that social work is considered a specialized profession that attempts to satisfy the needs of people through different society institutions, thereby concentrating on interaction between people and social systems that affect their abilities in achieving their hopes and ambitions, reinforcing their values, mitigating their suffering and helping them in solving the problems facing them using technical means.

Also, social work is considered by some people as a scientific fact that endeavours to realize an intended change in various society categories.

Methodological Framework

The current study aimed at investigating the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence and their attitudes towards it. To achieve this aim, the descriptive analytical approach was used.

- 1- **Study Methodology:** The current study adopted the descriptive analytical approach that is concerned with data collection, analysis and interpretation, in addition to the statistical treatment of variables and their correlations.
- 2- **Study Population:** The population of the study consisted of social work students at Al-Balqa Applied University in the first, second and third years, amounting to (476) male and female students distributed according to study year and gender, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1): Distribution of study population members according to Study year and gender

Year	Males	Females	Total
1	12	197	209
2	39	97	136
3	28	103	131
Total	79	397	476

- 3- **Study Sample:** The study sample was chosen using the layered random method, where (40%) and (100%) of females and males, respectively, were selected.

Table (2) illustrates the distribution of the study sample members according to the study variables.

Table (2): Study sample members according to study variables

Year	Males	Females	Total	Family educational level				Total
				Secondary and above		Less than secondary		
				Males	Females	Males	Females	
1	12	55	67	6	27	6	28	67

2	39	39	78	20	19	19	20	78
3	28	41	69	14	21	14	20	69
Total	99	135	234	40	67	39	68	234

- 4- **Study Tool:** The study adopted the questionnaire as a study tool to collect the required data. It was developed to suit the study objectives, depending on previous studies on the research subject, self-observation and theoretical readings on the topic.
- 5- **Tool Validity:** The validity of the research tool was confirmed through presenting it to a group of experts and referees who are specialized, experienced and scientifically qualified to express their opinions regarding the questionnaire, in terms of suitability of its items to the study objectives and the extent of their coverage of the intended aspects and fields. According to their remarks, some modifications were made to get the questionnaire in its final form.
- 6- **Tool Consistency:** It is intended to measure the extent of independency of the information about the study tool itself, with the aim of obtaining the same results when applied once again. To check the tool consistency, Cronbach's alpha coefficients were extracted for the questionnaire items as well as for the questionnaire as a whole. It was found that the study tool has a high consistency degree of more than (85%), which is considered sufficient for the purposes of the study from the perspective of statistics.
- 7- **Statistical Treatment:** In order to answer the study questions, arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' ratings on each of the items of the dimensions of the study tool as well as on each dimension as a whole were calculated. To detect the level of significance of differences in the students' ratings according to the study variables, independent samples T-test as well as one-way ANOVA test were used.

Presentation of Results

This section includes the presentation of the study results with the aim of investigating the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence. The results are presented through answering the study questions; as follows.

First Question: What is the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence and their attitudes towards it?

To answer this question, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of each relevant item in the study tool were calculated.

Table (3): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the awareness level of social work students of the concept of gender-based violence

No.	Awareness level of social work students of the concept of gender-based violence	Mean	Std. dev.	Level
1	Gender-based violence means an aggressive behaviour based on gender.	4.64	0.74	high
2	Gender-based violence means any act characterized by using force against someone who lacks it.	4.62	0.74	high
3	Gender-based violence means any act characterized by assault and ending with a problem in the familial environment.	4.44	0.84	high
4	Gender-based violence means various forms of physical, sexual, verbal and psychological harm practiced by a party to oblige another party to do certain acts or refrain from doing them.	4.42	0.84	high
5	Gender-based violence means taking the wife's own money or refraining from spending money for her and saying to her that she is not productive and spends much of the husband's money.	4.26	0.71	high
6	Actual assault or tending to commit assault and expressing feeling of anger towards the husband, the wife or both by means of hitting, insultation or cursing.	4.16	0.85	high
7	Gender-based violence means preventing husband, wife or both from expressing their opinions in social situations.	4.14	0.73	high
8	Gender-based violence means using force against women.	4.02	0.85	high
9	Gender-based violence means the rooting of masculine dominance culture in the society.	3.98	1.04	high
10	Marital assault in all its forms directly affects the woman's psychological and physical health.	3.96	1.04	high
11	Gender-based violence means the feeling to be lower when compared to others.	3.74	0.99	high

12	Gender-based violence is a problem that affects the familial pattern in all its components.	3.68	1.29	high
Awareness level of social work students of the concept of gender-based violence		4.17	0.75	high

It is noted from Table (3) that the awareness level of social work students of the concept of gender-based violence is high, with a mean of (4.17) and a standard deviation of (0.75), where all items of this axis came high, which means the clarity of the scientific concept to the study sample members, as all the items scored a high awareness level. Generally, this result can be attributed to that the sample members come from social and cultural backgrounds that enable them to form a clear position pertinent to gender-based violence and some of them might have own personal experiences, especially married female students.

Second Question: What is the awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence?

To answer this question, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of each relevant item in the study tool were calculated.

Table (4): Arithmetic means and standard deviation of awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence

No.	Awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence	Mean	Std. dev.	Level
1	Gender-based culture is among the causes of practicing violence.	4.04	0.61	high
2	Prevailing ideas of both gender types about each other is one reason of violence occurrence.	4.02	0.87	high
3	Previous experiences of husband and wife are among the causes of violence occurrence inside the familial environment.	3.96	0.76	high
4	Difficult economic conditions of families lead the woman to be a familial violence victim.	3.94	0.79	high
5	Prevalent religious interpretation gives the man the right of using violence against the woman to punish her.	3.94	0.79	high
6	Interventions by the relatives of husband and wife in familial affairs are among the causes of violence.	3.92	0.75	high

7	Witnessing violence incidents in the surrounding social environment encourages practicing violence.	3.60	1.07	high
8	The family in our society believes that the man has the right to punish the woman even by using violence.	3.12	1.06	high
9	Absence of sexual culture for husband and wife increases the gap of conflicts between them.	2.98	1.16	high
Awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence		3.72	0.54	high

From Table (4), it is noted that the awareness level of social work students of the causes of gender-based violence is high, with an arithmetic mean of (3.72) and a standard deviation of (0.54), where all items of this axis scored high levels of awareness, which means the clarity of the causes of gender-based violence to the study sample members, as all the items came with high awareness levels.

In general, the high awareness level of social work students of the causes leading to gender-based violence can be interpreted by their social and cultural backgrounds as well as their personal experiences, where practicing familial violence from their point of view is impacted by their personal experiences and their witnessing of familial violence incidents.

Third Question: What is the level of awareness of social work students of the forms of gender-based violence? To answer this question, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of each relevant item in the study tool were calculated.

Table (5): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of awareness level of social work students of the forms of gender-based violence

No.	Awareness level of social work students of the forms of gender-based violence	Mean	Std. dev.	Level
1	Hitting the woman or threatening to hit her is considered a form of gender-based violence.	4.18	0.87	high
2	Psychological and verbal violence against the woman is among the worst forms of violence against her.	4.18	0.87	high
3	Sexual violence or threatening to use it is considered among the forms of gender-based violence.	4.14	0.67	high
4	Threatening to deprive the woman is considered one of the forms of gender-based violence.	4.04	0.67	high

5	Preventing the husband/wife from expressing his/her opinion is one form of gender-based violence.	3.80	0.97	high
6	Threatening to take property by force is one of the forms of gender-based violence.	3.78	1.04	high
7	Emotional “dryness” between husband and wife is considered a form of gender-based violence.	3.70	1.00	high
Awareness level of social work students of the forms of gender-based violence		3.97	0.87	high

Table (5) shows that there are various forms of gender-based violence as perceived by social work students at the university, which range between hitting, cursing, insultation, deprivation and emotional dryness. The awareness level of students of the forms of gender-based violence came high on all the items of this axis, with arithmetic means ranging from (3.70) to (4.18) for the responses of study sample members. This result can be explained by the dominance of masculine mentality in the marital life scene in Arab societies, where the man practices his authority against the woman and treats her according to what he desires. This masculine mentality is a traditional culture that allows the man to treat the woman as a slave and practice violence against her. Often, what gives the man this legitimacy is the woman’s acceptance of being subject to violence by her husband, thinking that this would preserve the family’s entity.

Fourth Question: How do social work students look at the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women who are subject to violence? To answer this question, arithmetic means and standard deviations of the relevant items in the study tool were calculated.

Table (6): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the awareness level of social work students of the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women subject to violence

No.	Awareness level of social work students of the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women subject to violence	Mean	Std. dev.	Level
1	Social work courses at the university contain sufficient material about taking care of women subject to violence, which helps students understand the required taking care of the woman and dealing with her in the future.	4.04	0.61	high

2	Social work departments at the university are sufficiently concerned with field training courses at the institutions of taking care of women subject to violence.	4.02	0.87	high
3	The role of social work must include dealing with social policies related to taking care of women subject to violence.	3.96	0.76	high
4	Social work specialization helps students establish good social relationships with women who were subjected to one or more forms of violence.	3.94	0.79	high
5	I think that social work specialization is one of the important specializations in the Jordanian society, since it provides psychological and social support to women subject to violence.	3.94	0.79	high
6	I think that it is necessary to have social specialists working at all country's institutions.	3.92	0.75	high
7	Working in social work profession in the field of taking care of women subject to violence causes happiness and joy.	3.60	1.07	High
8	Answers that I presented in the questionnaire form reflect my personal point of view, my experience and my societal culture.	3.12	1.06	high
Awareness level of social work students of the role of social work profession in the field of taking care of women subject to violence		3.81	0.94	high

Table (6) indicates that the awareness level of social work students of the role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence was high, where all the items of this axis scored high evaluation degrees ranging from (3.12) to (4.04), while the total degree of this axis was (3.81) which expresses a high awareness level.

The study sample members see that the social work courses at the university were sufficient to provide them with information on gender-based violence and how to take care of women subject to violence. In general, one can say that social work students, in addition to being supported by the university to be academically and professionally prepared, are also members of the society in which they live, which of course affects their beliefs, opinions and societal culture formation. Here comes the role of the university in preparing social work students to be qualified to practice the social work profession in different fields, particularly the field of gender-based violence.

Fifth Question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the awareness level of social work students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence which can be attributed to gender (male, female), academic level (year 1, 2 and 3) and family's educational level (high, low)?

In order to examine the effects of gender, academic level and family's educational level on the students' awareness level of the phenomenon of gender-based violence, arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' evaluation degrees on the axes of the questionnaire and on the questionnaire as a whole were calculated. Then, the T-test was applied to extract the significance of differences between means. The results are illustrated in Table (7) and Table (8).

Table (7): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' scores on the measure according to the gender variable and the T-test results

Axis	Gender	Mean	Std. dev.	t	Sig.
Concept of gender-based violence	Male	34.29	3.85	- 0.611	0.543
	female	35.26	7.83		
Causes of gender-based violence	Male	39.61	4.61	1.693	0.095
	female	37.74	4.61		
Forms of gender-based violence	Male	28.29	4.42	0.201	0.842
	female	28.06	4.76		
Role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence	Male	36.82	4.23	1.205	0.232
	female	35.47	4.96		
Total	Male	139.00	10.68	0.902	0.371
	female	136.53	11.89		

It is evident from Table (7) that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the students' estimations of their awareness level of the phenomenon of gender-based violence which can be attributed to gender, where the level of significance amounted to (0.371) which is higher than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This means that gender has no impact on the awareness level of the students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence.

Table (8): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' scores on the measure according to the variable of family's educational level and the T-test results

Axis	Family's educational level	Mean	Std. dev.	t	Sig.
Concept of gender-based violence	high	35.31	7.63	0.740	0.462
	low	34.13	4.08		
Causes of gender-based violence	high	38.73	4.97	0.749	0.456
	low	37.88	4.05		
Forms of gender-based violence	high	28.67	4.52	1.368	0.176
	low	27.15	4.68		
Role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence	high	35.76	4.95	-0.547	0.586
	low	36.38	4.32		
Total	high	138.47	12.43	1.156	0.252
	low	135.54	9.24		

It is clear from Table (8) that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the students' estimations of their awareness level of the phenomenon of gender-based violence which can be attributed to the family's educational level, where the level of significance amounted to (0.252) which is higher than the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). This means that the family's educational level has no impact on the awareness level of students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence.

Regarding the effect of academic level on the awareness degree of the phenomenon of gender-based violence, arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' scores on the measure were calculated. Then, one-way ANOVA was used to determine the significance of differences between the variables.

Tables (9) and (10) illustrate the analysis results.

Table (9): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the students' scores on the measure according to the variable of academic level

Axis	Academic level	Mean	Std. dev.
Concept of gender-based violence	1	33.88	3.71
	2	36.84	10.10
	3	33.96	3.62
	Total	34.89	6.61
Causes of gender-based violence	1	37.52	5.35
	2	38.28	3.51
	3	39.52	4.91
	Total	38.44	4.67
Forms of gender-based violence	1	28.32	3.54
	2	28.16	5.42
	3	27.96	4.83
	Total	28.15	4.61
Role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence	1	34.48	4.90
	2	36.28	4.59
	3	37.16	4.44
	Total	35.97	4.72
Total degree	1	134.20	10.05
	2	139.56	11.85
	3	138.60	12.06
	Total	137.45	11.44

Table (10): Results of one-way ANOVA of the significance of differences between means according to the variable of academic level

Axis	Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of squares	F	Sig.
Concept of gender-based violence	between groups	142.19	2	71.09	1.654	0.198
	inside groups	304.96	72	42.99		
Causes of gender-based violence	between groups	50.96	2	25.48	1.176	0.314
	inside groups	1559.52	72	21.66		
Forms of gender-based violence	between groups	1.63	2	0.81	0.037	0.963
	inside groups	1567.76	72	21.77		
Role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence	between groups	93.31	2	46.65	2.161	0.123
	inside groups	1554.64	72	21.59		
Total degree	between groups	408.43	2	204.21	1.584	0.212
	inside groups	9282.16	72	128.92		

Table (10) reveals that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the students' estimations of their awareness level of the phenomenon of gender-based violence on each of the axes of the measure, where the levels of significance of all the axes were higher than the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), which means no impact of academic level on the awareness level of students of the phenomenon of gender-based violence.

Discussion of Results

1- The statistical analysis results revealed the existence of positive attitudes of social work student at Al-Balqa Applied University towards the concept of gender-based violence, confirming that violence is an aggressive behaviour which must be fought to achieve stability inside the family. This finding reflects the awareness level of the study sample members of the phenomenon of gender-based violence. Also, the statistical analysis results confirm the extent of clarity of the scientific concept of

the phenomenon of gender-based violence, where the sample members know that violence is an aggressive behaviour which is based on gender. Consequently, the students will work in the future to treat this phenomenon through the theoretical and applied preparation which they acquired at their university. This result came in contradiction to Al-Awawdeh (2018) who found that the level of knowledge and skills of social specialists is still lower than required in the field of familial violence. However, the current study is consistent with Al-Mufti and Al-Arabeed (2018) who confirmed the necessity of providing women subject to violence with the required skills and strategies to face violence against them.

- 2- Regarding violence causes and forms, the statistical analysis results revealed the existence of positive attitudes of social work students at Al-Balqa Applied University towards the causes and forms of gender-based violence. So, their awareness level of these causes and forms was high. This finding agrees with Bruckner (2006) who emphasized that violence leads to the occurrence of weakness in the internal means of social control represented in conscience saturated with the values, habits and traditions of the society, which results in that the internal social control means lose their power in confronting and fighting deviating behaviour which harms others, specifically violence against women. Also, the current study agrees with Abeer Yousef (2020) who emphasized the importance of the economic factor-particularly husband's poverty- in practicing violence against the wife.
- 3- Regarding the awareness level of social work students of the role of social work profession in taking care of women subject to violence, the statistical analysis results showed the existence of a high awareness level in the study sample members of this role. This indicates the positive role of the university in allowing the students to acquire theoretical information and knowledge as well as the skills that qualify them to form this position through preparing them academically and practically, in addition to their personal experiences in this field. This finding agrees with Hawasa Jamal (2019) who confirmed the importance of the role of social service in reducing familial problems, specifically familial violence and emphasized the importance of the applied dimension and professional practice in reducing familial violence in the society.
- 4- The statistical analysis results showed no statistically significant differences in the means of the study sample members in the four dimensions that can be attributed to

the study variables (gender, family's educational level and students' academic level). This could be due to that the phenomenon of gender-based violence is completely clear at the conceptual level to the study sample members, which can be attributed to the similarity of cultural and social environments in which sample members of both gender types live, noting that they are subject to the same social, economic, political and cultural conditions and challenges, in addition to that they receive the same education, where they study the same discipline (social work), resulting in possessing nearly the same experience and leading to having nearly the same awareness level of the phenomenon of violence based on gender.

Recommendations

In light of the study results, the following recommendations are presented:

- Conducting more research on the awareness of gender-based violence and its effects on other samples and societies employed in the current study.
- Conducting a study on the role of the family in social upbringing in the shadow of social, cultural, economic and political changes witnessed by societies from time to time.

References

- Al-Awawdah, Amal. (2018). Attitudes of Social Specialists toward Gender-based Violence Cases. *Journal of Islamic University for Human Sciences*, Vol. (26), No. (2), Gaza.
- Al-Ayesh, Zainab. (2016). Familial Violence: Causes and Treatment. *Journal of Abdulaziz University- Arts and Human Sciences*, No. (11), Jeddah, KSA.
- Al-Hassan, Ihsan and Al-Ahmad, Adnan. (2009). *Introduction to Sociology*. 2nd Edn., Wa'el House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Hassan, Ihsan. (2008). *Crime Sociology*. Wa'el House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Hassan, Ihsan. (2008). *Woman's Sociology: Analytical Study of the Woman's Role in the Contemporary Society*. Amman, Wa'el House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Mufti, Amjad and Al-Arabeed, Ahmad. (2018). Professional Vision of Public Practice in Social Service to Deal with Women Who Are Victims of Violence. Paper

- published in the study day entitled: *Violence against the Woman: Risks and Solutions*, Islamic University, Gaza, Palestine.
- Awwad, Yousef Diab. (2012). Factors Associated with the Woman Causing Her Being Subject to Violence by Her Husband from the Perspective of Psychological, Social and Law Specialists Working with Women Subject to Violence. *Journal of Hebron University for Research*, Vol. (7), No. (1), Hebron, Palestine.
- Bruckner, M. (2006). Domestic Violence: Local Activities-International Issues. *Journal of Social Work & Society*, 4 (1), 1-8.
- Duvvury, Nata and Galway, Nui. (2009). *Keeping Gender on the Agenda: Gender-based Violence, Poverty and Development*. Irish Joint Consortium on GBV.
- Family Protection Administration. (2020). *Statistics of Violence against the Woman*. Public Security Department, Amman, Jordan.
- Hassan, Wahbah. (2001). *Assaulting the Woman: Study on the Marital Relationship Psychodynamics*. PhD Dissertation, Faculty of Arts, Zaqaziq University, Egypt.
- Hinkle, R. (1994). *The Development of Modern Sociology*. New York, Random House, p.39.
- ICRW. (2009). *Intimate Partner Violence: High Costs to Household and Communities*. Washington DC: International Center for Research on Women.
- Jamal, Hawasa. (2019). Role of Social Service in Reducing Familial Problems: Familial Violence As a Model. *Journal of Human and Social Studies*, Vol. (9), Oran University 2, Algeria.
- Jamil, Asma'a. (2007). *Social Violence: Study of Some of Its Aspects in the Iraqi Society*. Public Cultural Affairs House, Baghdad, Iraq.
- Leung, Lai. (2011). Gender Sensitivity among Social Workers Handling Cases of Domestic Violence: A Hong Kong Case. *Journal of Women and Social Work*, 26 (3), 291-303.
- Newman, C. (1993). Giving up: Shelter Experiences of Battered Woman. *Public Health Nursing*.
- Oyediran, K.A. and I.-A. U. (2005). Perceptions of Nigerian Women on Domestic Violence: Evidence from 2003 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey. *Afr. J. Reprod.*, 9, 38-53.

- Peedicayil, A., Sadowski, L.S., Jeyaseelan, L., Shankar, V., Jain, D., Suresh, S. et al. (2004). Spousal Physical Violence against Women during Pregnancy. *Br. J. Obstet. Gynaecol.*, 111, 682-687.
- Qassim, Amani. (2009). Towards a Proposed Program to Develop the Role of Social Specialists in Working with Familial Violence Cases. *Journal of Studies in Social Service and Human Sciences*, Part (1), No. (2), Helwan University, Egypt.
- Redcross, Joseph W. (2002). *Negligent Action Arising from Violent Acts in Public and Private Schools*. related:mlis.state.md.us/2002rs/misc/Major_Issues_Review_1999-2002.pdf
- Richardson, J., Coid, J., Petruckevitch, A., Chung, W.S., Moorey, S. and Feder, G. (2002). Identifying Domestic Violence: Cross-sectional Study in Primary Care. *BMJ*, , -280.
- UNICEF. (2000). Domestic Violence against Women and Girls. *Innocent Digest*. Yousef, Abeer. (2020). Problems of the Woman Subject to Violence and the Role of Common Practice in Social Service in Reducing Them. *Journal of Studies in Social Service and Human Sciences*, Vol. (1), No. (49), Helwan University, Egypt.